

EWA-BELT

Linking East and West African farming systems experience
into a BELT of sustainable intensification

Maize ISFM

Economic and environmental viability of organic fertilisation for sustainable maize production in Africa

Policy Brief n. 1

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SUMMARY

There is a need for sustainable maize production in Africa due to growing food demand and declining soil fertility. This policy brief recommends the promotion and upscaling of organic fertilizer and integrated soil fertility management (ISFM) options for sustainable maize production in east and west Africa regions based on findings from research carried out in Ghana and Kenya under the EWA-BELT project. Strategies to increase organic fertilizer production should be pursued by governments and all stakeholders.

- Maize yields increase under all three fertiliser options (inorganic, organic and integrated inorganic and organic fertiliser options) in both the short to long term. However, yields increase at a greater rate under the full organic fertiliser option than under the inorganic or integrated inorganic and organic options, producing the highest yields in the long term due to improved soil health.
- All fertiliser options are profitable in both the short- to long-term, but the organic fertiliser generates the highest benefits in both the short- and long-term.
- Proportional increases in output price and input costs to account for inflation result in increased farm profit.

The main limiting factor to organic fertiliser use is the lack of organic fertiliser

BACKGROUND

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most important cereal crops in Africa, covering about 40 million hectares which are mainly under smallholder production, producing about 81 million tonnes a year (FAOSTAT, 2019). Maize plays a leading role in global food security, and is mostly used for human consumption and for animal feed. It accounts for about 34% of the total worldwide cereal production, with an average of 750 million metric tons produced annually. In East Africa, in particular, it represents 45% of the caloric intake; hence, it is crucial for the population and economy of these regions (Shiferaw et al., 2011). In Ghana, it accounts for more than one-quarter of calories consumed (GSS 2018). The limiting factors to maize production in Ghana and Kenya include; poor soils, poor rain fall distribution, high fertilizer prices, climatic variability, inadequate crop varieties, pests and diseases, and high postharvest losses. Declining soil fertility is a major problem in sub-Saharan African agriculture (Vanlauwe et al., 2017). Continuous cropping has considerably contributed to soil fertility decline in Ghana (Kanton et al., 2016). Inorganic fertilisers are frequently restricted to supply of NPK. However, organic fertilisers offer a wide range of micronutrients and soil organic matter, promoting the development of the plant and the surrounding ecosystem. Plants with high nutrient availability grow faster and produce more yield. It has been empirically established that there is an environmental benefit derived from using organic fertiliser (Dick, et al., 2004; Conway & Barber, 1990; Hui, et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2018), however, there is a need to understand the socio-economic implications of introducing sustainable practices like organic fertiliser in crop production, hence this study.

Maize ISFM

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APPROACH

This study was conducted in Ghana (west Africa) and in Kenya (east Africa). Two types of fertilisers were examined at farm scale: manure, as the organic option, and NPK with ammonia as the inorganic alternative. In Ghana, three treatments were considered: i) full inorganic, using 250 kg of NPK with 125 kg of ammonia per ha; ii) full organic, employing 6,000 kg of manure per ha; and iii) integrated, combining organic and inorganic at a half proportion of the conventional, utilising 125 kg of NPK, 63 kg ammonia and 3,000 kg of manure per ha. In Kenya the treatment were; i) full inorganic, using 190 kg of NPK; ii) full organic, employing 2,000 kg of manure per ha; and iii) integrated, combining organic and inorganic at a half proportion of the conventional, utilising 80 kg of NPK, 1,000 kg of manure per ha. Other inputs (i.e., herbicides, pesticides, seeds) were kept constant since they are directly related to the size of the farm and the number of plants per hectare (i.e., spacing) (Taylor, 2020; True, 2021). Herbicides and pesticides were applied twice over the production period.

Economic data analysis was performed to assess the economic viability of the three fertiliser options. Yan & Gong (2010) models were used to predict maize yield increases in the short to long term.

Figure 1: Three fertilizer treatments and maize

Maize ISFM

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FINDINGS

The analyses were done on a per hectare basis to allow for easy comparison. In Kenya, the treatment with the highest average maize yield was the integrated fertilizer option with 7.2 t/ha followed by the organic option with 6.1 t/ha and then inorganic with 5.8 t/ha. In Ghana, the integrated option also recorded the highest average maize yield of 3.4 t/ha followed by the inorganic option with 2.4 t/ha and then the organic option with 1.4 t/ha. The yields from Kenya were generally higher than those of Ghana, however, the integrated fertilizer option yield was consistently higher across the two countries (see Figure 2 a & d).

Figure 2: Comparing economic variables of Ghana & Kenya

The gross revenue estimated was \$3,096 for the integrated option for Kenya and \$1,543 for the Ghana integrated fertilizer option. The total production cost for Kenya was consistently higher than that for Ghana across all three treatments. The inorganic fertilizer option had the highest total production cost for Kenya at \$553 and in Ghana, the highest production cost was for the integrated option at \$351. In Kenya the treatment with the lowest production cost was the organic option and in Ghana it was the inorganic fertilizer option that had the lowest cost of production (see Figure 2b).

The integrated fertilizer option had the highest gross margins in Kenya and Ghana with \$2,565 and \$1,192 respectively. The lowest gross margin was for the inorganic treatment in Kenya and organic treatment in Ghana (see Figure 2f). All treatments across both countries had benefit cost ratios above 1.5 indicating that they were all profitable.

Figure 3: Return to Labour, Benefit cost ratio (BCR), and Return on Investment (ROI)

Maize ISFM

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The integrated option however had the highest BCR across both countries with that for Kenya being 5.8 and that for Ghana being 4.4. The highest returns on investment were also observed with the integrated options across both countries (see Figure 3).

The yield of maize for the three fertilizer options in Kenya and Ghana was predicted over a 30-year period horizon using long-term yield relationships in Yan & Gong (2010). The yield of all the treatment options consistently increased over the period. However, the increase in the full organic option increased at a higher rate compared to the full inorganic and the integrated options. This trend resulted in the full organic option delivering higher yields by year 17 in Kenya and in Ghana by year 26. This is followed by the integrated option obtaining the second highest yield by year 17 in Kenya and in Ghana by year 27.

Figure 4: Yields and gross margins predicted over 30 years horizon using.

YIELD AND PROFITABILITY

In Kenya, the integrated fertilizer option gave the highest average maize yield at 7.2 t/ha followed by the full organic treatment at 6.1 t/ha and then the full inorganic treatment with 5.8 t/ha. These are all higher than the average maize grain yield in Kenya which is estimated to be about 1.77 t/ha (FAOSTAT, 2019). It has been established that Kenya has a maize yield potential of about 10 t/ha in high-yielding areas (Ittersum et al., 2016). It has also been established that the relationship between yield and soil organic carbon is linear (Yan & Gong, 2010). The use of organic fertilizer increased soil organic carbon and soil fertility and consequently resulted in a larger yield when compared to chemical fertilization. In Ghana, Bidzakin et al. (2023) also concluded that farmers who used organic fertilizers in their maize production obtained higher yields, income and gross margins than those who did not.

In Ghana, the integrated option also had the highest average maize yield of 3.4 t/ha followed by the inorganic option at 2.4 t/ha and then the organic option at 1,425kg. The average yield of maize on farmers' fields in northern Ghana is approximately 1.6 t/ha compared to a potential of 5.5 t/ha (MoFA, 2017) and the national average is 2.5 t/ha (MoFA, 2021). The yields from Kenya were generally higher than those of Ghana because the site in Ghana was a low-yielding area whilst in Kenya, the site was in a high-yielding area. However, the integrated fertilizer option yield was consistently higher across the two countries in the short-term, whilst in the long-term, the full organic option had the highest yields.

The integrated fertilizer option was more profitable in Kenya and Ghana with gross margins of \$2,565 and \$1,192 respectively. The least profitable options were the inorganic treatment for Kenya and organic treatment for Ghana. All three fertilizer treatments were profitable across both countries with benefit-cost ratios (BCR) above 1.5. The integrated option however recorded the highest BCR across both countries with Kenya at 5.8 and Ghana at 4.4. This was similar to the findings reported by Bidzakin et al. (2023) and Bidzakin et al. (2014). The treatment with the highest return on investment was the integrated option across both countries in the short-run whilst in the long-run the most profitable option was the full organic option.

The study suggests that in the short-term, the integrated fertilizer option is the more profitable option when compared to the full inorganic and full organic options. However, in the long-term the full organic option appears to provide the highest yields and net margins. The organic fertilizer treatment is recommended as the most economical and environmentally friendly option for sustainable maize production in Africa.

CONCLUSIONS & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The results show that all the treatments are profitable in the short- and long-term. However, the integrated fertilizer option appeared to be most profitable in the short-term whilst the organic fertilizer option was most profitable in the long-term. The organic fertilizer option also has the greatest potential to improve soil health for sustainable crop production in the long-term. Hence, if possible, in the long-term, we suggest the promotion and adoption of full organic fertilization for sustainable maize crop production. This could be done with the integrated fertilizer option to ensure farmers are able to maintain economic gains in the short- to medium-term without compromising the capacity of the soil to support future crop production.

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